

Analysis And Design of Plate Girder Using in STAAD.Pro

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Abstract— The substantial growth in both population and traffic are likely to bring about several changes in the use and construction of different types of bridges. Plate girders and tee girders are the superstructures used in bridges the most frequently. This study effort has studied and constructed plate girders and Tee girders using the WSM (working state method) IS 800:1984 and LSM (limit state method) IS 800:2007 in STAAD-pro software as well as by manual computation to find the most appropriate form of bridge superstructure. The present study is done to design the structure of plate girder considering traffic loading and other forces i.e., dead load, live load and comparing the working state method and limit state method. In this research steel plate girder structure is taken for comparing the working state method and limit state method in this project The code used are IS 800:1984 and IS 800:2007 for design of girder for the road bridge. It is found that in the limit state method, the design load is obtained by multiplying the load's partial safety factors to the work load and the working stress method is less economical as it gives thicker parts as compare to limit state method which is more economical because it gives thin sections.

Keywords— Plate Girder, STAAD PRO, Working State Method, Limit State Method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bridge girders made of steel plate are cambered to accommodate deflections that arise during construction. In general, a bridge that uses girders to support the deck is known as a girder bridge. It's highly likely that girder bridges are the most widely constructed and used kind of bridges

worldwide. In its most basic form, its architecture is like a log.

Stretching over a river or brook from one side to the other. When discussing bridge design, the terms "girder" and "beam" are frequently used interchangeably. Some publications do, however, define beam bridges somewhat differently than girder bridges.

While IS 800-1984 is based on the working stress approach, IS 800-2007 is based on the limit state method. Limit state is the allowable upper bound on the safety and serviceability standards prior to failure. A structure that maintains an acceptable level of reliability and won't become unfit for usage is the goal of limit state design. Standard IS 800 is widely used and recognized by technical institutions, industry, professional bodies, and engineers.

A bridge with two or more plate girders supporting it is called a plate girder bridge. Instead of being rolled into a single cross section, the plate girder is normally composed of I-beams that are joined by bolts, rivets, or welding.

form the beam's horizontal flanges and vertical web. James Millholland constructed the first tubular wrought iron plate girder bridge for the Baltimore and Ohio Railroad in 1846. These bridge types can accommodate trains, highways, and other types of traffic and are appropriate for short to medium spans. The length restriction is determined by the method of transportation utilized to get the girder from the fabricator to the construction site, and it is often prefabricated.

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Figure 1: Class A loading

II. OBJECTIVES

- To analysis and design the plate girder by using WSM method in excel sheet.
- To analysis and design the plate girder by using WSM method in STAAD-Pro software.
- To analysis and design the plate girder by using LSM method in EXCEL sheet.
- To analysis and design plate girder bridge by using LSM method in STAAD-Pro software.
- To compare the design of steel Plate girder, result for LSM & WSM.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter provides a chronological review of bridge failure history and causes. The utilization of shear connectors and advancements in composite open web steel girder bridge technology are also examined. The benefits and drawbacks of using high tensile strength steel in bridge are discussed. The following three subheadings describe the body of literature now in existence about the causes of steel bridge collapse and composite open web steel girder bridges with RCC decks.

- i. A synopsis of bridge failure throughout history.
- ii. Steel girder technology for buildings and bridges made of composite open web.
- iii. Shear connectors in steel girder bridges with composite open webs.

A. A Recent Report Of Bridges' Failure

Numerous steel bridges have fallen in the past at different points during their construction and operation. While some failures were complete collapses, others were only partial. Among the most common reasons for failure include poor design, overstressing of structural components, poor building techniques, fatigue and creep, carelessness and lack of inspection, unintentional impacts on bridges, earthquakes, fire damage, and other unanticipated events. The most frequent reasons for failure in open web steel bridges are buckling of the twelve compression members and connection failure.

The list of 31 bridge failures in the USA from 1980 to 2009 indicates that one bridge failed every eight months on average, and from 2010 to 2012, 27 bridges were reported to have failed, with one bridge falling on average every month (construction risk management, 2012).

The abrupt collapse of steel girder bridges with open webs is caused by the buckling of non-redundant critical compression members. Tension members, in contrast to compression members, typically do not fail abruptly because they exhibit observable elongation and have the capacity to withstand stresses greater than the yield stress. Because tension and compression members behave quite differently under load, compression members require a distinct design methodology.

B. Important Bridge Failure Caused By Buckling

When it comes to open web steel girder bridges, buckling of the connecting plates or top chord member is the most frequent reason for the superstructure to fail. A structure may collapse abruptly or gradually over time. When a structure has progressive failure, it is simple to assess the problem and take preventative action to fix it. Failures that happen gradually also offer us time to prevent fatalities. But in the event of an abrupt failure, the entire structure can fall apart without any prior notice in a matter of seconds. In addition to property loss, this could result in fatalities.

C. Failure Of The Chauras Bridge, Which Is Being Built

In Uttarakhand, India, a 190-meter-long bridge was planned to be built across the Alaknanda River close to Srinagar. Between the cities of Chauras on the right bank and Srinagar on the left, a bridge was to be built. The bridge's three spans were each 40 meters, 110 meters, and 40 meters long continuous open web steel girders. On March 24, 2012, the bridge collapsed when the concrete deck slab was being installed (H.S. Birajdar et al., 2014) (Figure 2.9). The mishap claimed the lives of six people.

D. Advances In Steel Girder Technology For Composite Open Web Applications

The 1960s saw the start of experimental research on composite open web steel girder bridges (Azmi, 1972). Five experimental studies on conventional and composite open-web steel joists with 6.1 m spans for buildings were carried out in 1965 (Lembeck, 1965). By embedding the projection of the web of members into a concrete slab above the top chord, the system was transformed into a composite. Comparing composite and non-composite joists with the same tension chord, it was found that the former were stronger and stiffer. Lembeck also came to the conclusion that a significant reduction in the amount of steel used in the joist's upper chord was possible. Four tests on composite and non-composite steel trusses in the elastic range were carried out by Wang and Kaley in 1967. Additionally, they noticed a notable decrease in tensions and deflection.

E. Laboratory Tests For Composite Action Analysis

Over the past few decades, there has been an increase in study on composite open web steel girder bridges; nevertheless, the majority of this research has been on composite plate girder bridge in bridge construction.. A few case studies of lab experiments that have been published on under-slung and composite deck construction in bridges.

IV. HISTORY OF CODE COMPARISONS

In the industry, comparing different design codes is nothing new. One popular piece of software for testing loads, doing analyses, and designing small- to medium-sized bridges is called SAM. They compared the British Standard and Eurocodes to the pre-tensioned bridge design in their study. They used UK National Annex after designing a basic concrete bridge deck with BS 5400. The deck was built with UK-standard Y3 beams at 1 meter centers and combined two 20-meter spans with a 25° skew that were made continuous over the central support and carried a single carriageway. A live load sagging moment of 384 kNm and a hogging moment of 328 kNm were the specifications for the BS 5400 beam. Nevertheless, the Eurocodes beam.

Wsm Method	Symbol	Staad Pro	Manual
Maximum Bending Moment, BM (Service)	BM	3124kN/m	3616 kN/m
Maximum Bending Moment, Mz (Factored)	Mz	4356 kN/m	4468 kN/m
Maximum Shear Force, SF	SF	592 kN	597 kN
Factored Shear Force, V	V	868 kN	872 kN

Lsm Method	Symbol	Staad Pro	Manual
Maximum Bending Moment, BM (Service)	BM	2850kN/m	2550 kN/m
Maximum Bending Moment, Mz (Factored)	Mz	4275kN/m	4268 kN/m
Maximum Shear Force, SF	SF	570kN	565 kN
Factored Shear Force, V	V	855kN	836 kN

Whole Structure Loads 17.5127kN:1m Fx 875.634kN:1m
Displacements 39.3701in:1m Beam Stress 196.85in:m 1 DL

Whole Structure Loads 17.5127kN:1m Fz 175.127kN:1m
Fy 175.127kN:1m Fx 875.634kN:1m Displacements
39.3701in:1m 1 DL

Whole Structure Loads 17.5127kN:1m My 7874.02kip-in:1m
Mz 7874.02kip-in:1m Displacements 39.3701in:1m 1 DL

designing By WSD Adopting Flange Width as 300 mm and Flange Thickness as 35mm.

Thus, Total depth of the Plate Girder, $D=1380.00$ for lsm and 1082 for wsm.

CONCLUSION

The investigation mentioned above leads to the following findings. A code of practice guarantees security by outlining specific minimal requirements for the design. This document presents significant clauses from IS 800-1984 and IS 800-2007. The new IS 800 – 2007 code for plate girder design is far more efficient than the previous one.

Because the IS 800 - 2007 code incorporates additional provisions and advances sustainable design, it is appropriate for the state of design practice today.

Most designers and construction authorities primarily use the most recent code of practice. Also, this study concludes that, analysing plate girder with Staad pro reduces manual computations and consequently provides correct results in less time.

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WSM METHOD	SYMBOL	STAAD PRO	MANUAL
Width of flange bf1	m	0.300	0.279
Thickness of web	m	0.016	0.015
Width of flange bf2	m	0.300	0.279
Total width of girder	m	1.082	1.083

LSM METHOD	SYMBOL	STAAD PRO	MANUAL
Width of flange bf1	m	0.350	0.334
Thickness of web	m	0.020	0.017
Width of flange bf2	m	0.350	0.0336
Total width of girder	m	1.380	1.322

V. RESULT ANALYSIS

The result of the computations above is as follows.

Thus the minimum web thickness is 19.40 mm from manual calculation.

Hence provide thickness of web, t_w is 20 mm for lsm and 16 mm for wsm.

Hence Adopting Web Depth as 1300mm and Web Thickness as 20mm for LSD and for WSD 1380mm and 16mm.

Sizing Of Flange

In order to maximize the moment capacity, the cross section of the plastic girder should be proportioned that it satisfies the requirements of plastic/compact sections.

Thus,

Ratio b/t_f 8.4 for plastic section for LSM

Assuming Width of flange bf 390 mm

Provide, bf 300 mm by using wsm method and Provide, bf 350 mm by using lsm method

Assuming Thickness of flange, $t_f > 20.83$

Provide, t_f 40.00 mm for lsm and 35.00 mm for wsm.

Hence for designing by LSD purpose Adopting Flange Width as 350mm and Flange Thickness as 40mm and also for

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